

GRADUATE NURSING STUDENTS' SELF-EFFICACY AND SATISFACTION ON EARTHQUAKE DISASTER RESPONSE SIMULATION-BASED LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the self-efficacy and satisfaction of graduate nursing students at Holy Name University, batch 2022-2023, regarding Earthquake Disaster Response Simulation-Based Learning (SBL). It focuses on various aspects, including knowledge, skills, values, attitudes, context, background, and simulation design. Additionally, it investigates the relationship between self-efficacy and self-satisfaction in the context of earthquake disaster response training. Using a quantitative descriptive correlational design, data was collected through a self-made questionnaire. The data were analyzed using weighted means, and the significance of relationships was assessed using a t-test. The study's findings indicated that participation in disaster response SBL significantly enhances students' knowledge, skills, and attitude-related self-efficacy. High levels of satisfaction reported by participants point to the importance of SBL in providing an engaging and impactful learning experience. Moreover, a significant positive correlation was found between self-efficacy and satisfaction, emphasizing the interdependence of these factors in shaping students' perceptions of their preparedness. These findings have important implications for nursing education, indicating that integrating SBL into curricula can boost students' confidence and competence in disaster response. It is essential for

educators to continue incorporating SBL into nursing programs and to further explore the relationship between self-efficacy, satisfaction, and preparedness. This approach aims to optimize educational outcomes and ultimately improve patient care in emergency situations.

Keywords: *Self-efficacy, Satisfaction, Earthquake Simulation-based learning, Disaster Response*

INTRODUCTION

Graduate nursing students acquire essential clinical competencies through direct exposure to real medical and surgical cases. However, responding to disasters, particularly earthquake emergencies, requires a different set of skills beyond routine patient care. Unlike controlled hospital settings where nursing students follow structured protocols, disaster response situations demand rapid decision-making, adaptability, and resilience under high-pressure conditions (Alim, Kawabata, & Nakazawa, 2015). Given the increasing frequency and severity of disasters, it is critical to prepare nursing students not only in theoretical knowledge but also in hands-on experience to enhance their self-efficacy and satisfaction in disaster response training (Gooding et al., 2022).

Simulation-based learning has emerged as a widely used and effective method for disaster preparedness training. It provides nursing students with near-realistic emergency scenarios that simulate mass casualty incidents, equipping them with the skills and confidence needed to respond effectively (Brinjee, Al Thobaity, Almalki, & Alahmari, 2021). Unlike traditional classroom learning, simulation-based disaster training allows students to engage in lifelike crisis situations, applying their knowledge in controlled yet high-intensity environments (Kim, Park, & Shin, 2016). Research has demonstrated that simulation-based learning significantly enhances nursing students' preparedness, particularly when the simulations closely mimic real-life conditions and challenges (AlOtaibi et al., 2024).

A critical factor in the effectiveness of disaster simulation training is self-efficacy, which refers to an individual's belief in their ability to successfully perform specific tasks. Higher self-efficacy among nursing students has been linked to better performance, improved decision-making, and increased confidence in handling emergency situations (Alim et al., 2015). In the context of disaster response, students with greater self-efficacy are more likely to remain composed under pressure, apply their skills effectively, and contribute meaningfully to crisis situations (Brinjee et al., 2021). Studies indicate that well-designed simulation-based training programs significantly enhance self-efficacy by offering repeated exposure to disaster scenarios, allowing students to practice and refine their skills (Kim et al., 2016).

Beyond self-efficacy, satisfaction with disaster simulation training plays a crucial role in ensuring its effectiveness. Satisfaction is influenced by various factors, including the realism of the simulation, the quality of instructional design, student engagement, and opportunities for active participation (AlOtaibi et al., 2024). A well-structured simulation that mimics real-world disaster conditions can boost students' motivation and engagement, leading to a more effective and immersive learning experience (Gooding et al., 2022). Conversely, limitations such as one-time simulations, imbalanced role assignments, and lack of follow-up training may hinder learning outcomes, leading to decreased confidence in real-life disaster scenarios (Haahr et al., 2020). Research suggests that repeated exposure to simulation-based disaster training enhances both learning retention and preparedness, reinforcing students' confidence in their ability to respond effectively (Labrague & De Los Santos, 2020).

Given the vital role of nurses in disaster response, it is essential to explore the relationship between self-efficacy and satisfaction in earthquake disaster simulation-based learning. Understanding how these factors influence nursing students' preparedness can inform the development of more effective and engaging disaster training programs (Gooding et al., 2022). By evaluating graduate nursing students' self-efficacy and satisfaction with earthquake disaster response simulations, this study aims to provide valuable insights into improving disaster education. The findings will contribute to enhancing the design of simulation-based disaster training, ensuring that future nursing professionals are adequately prepared to respond confidently and effectively to real-world disaster scenarios.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to determine the self-efficacy and satisfaction with the earthquake disaster response simulation-based learning of the graduate nursing students' batch 2022-2023 and specifically answer these questions:

1. What is the self-efficacy of the participants to the earthquake disaster simulation-based learning in terms of:
 - a. Knowledge preparedness ;
 - b. Skills preparedness; and
 - c. Attitudes preparedness?
2. What is the self-satisfaction of the participants to the earthquake disaster simulation-based learning in terms of:
 - a. Context ;
 - b. Background; and
 - c. Simulation design?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the self-efficacy and self-satisfaction of the participants to the earthquake disaster response simulation-based learning?
4. What recommendations can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative descriptive correlational design to determine graduate nursing students' self-efficacy and satisfaction to the Earthquake Disaster Response Simulation-Based Learning. The study explained the relationship between two or more variables without making claims about cause and effect. The participants were selected by random sampling using the fishbowl technique. The study utilized the quantitative method, pilot-tested survey questionnaire to gather the needed data.

Research Environment

The study was conducted at Holy Name University, located on J.A. Clarin Street in Tagbilaran City, Bohol, as well as at BPSTEA, situated at 0432 Tamblot Circumferential Road, Tagbilaran City, Bohol. Additionally, the research was conducted online using Google Forms for participants who were staying outside of Bohol. These locations served as the sites where the research participants resided during their review for the board exam following graduation.

Research Participants

The participants in this study were primarily nursing graduates from the Holy Name University, College of Health Sciences, specifically from Batch 2022-2023, consisting of a total of 154 students. To achieve a confidence level of 95%, ensuring that the actual value falls within $\pm 5\%$ of the measured value, at least 111 students were required to participate. Additionally, twenty respondents were selected for pilot testing of the questionnaire and were not included in the 111 chosen participants.

The participants attended a 5-day lecture and return demonstration focused on disaster response, followed by an earthquake disaster response simulation-based learning experience organized by Holy Name University in collaboration with the CDRRMO and Tarsier 117. Holy Name University is the only institution in Bohol that offers disaster response simulation-based learning, which is assisted and supervised by the CDRRMO and Tarsier 117.

Research Instrument

The study utilized a quantitative descriptive correlational research design. A modified questionnaire was developed to collect data on the level of self-efficacy and satisfaction with the learning experience, drawing from related literature and modified by the research team. The questionnaires were administered to participants in person using a checklist survey.

The researchers developed a checklist survey questionnaire based on three studies. The first study, Satisfaction of Medical Students with Simulation-Based Learning,

was conducted by Agha et al. (2015). The second study, Medical Student Satisfaction and Confidence in Simulation-Based Learning in Rwanda – Pre and Post-Simulation Survey Research, was authored by Turatsinze et al. (2020). The third study, The Effect of Simulation-Based Training on Nursing Students' Communication Skills, Self-Efficacy, and Clinical Competence for Nursing Practice, was conducted by Mohamed and Fashafsheh (2019).

The questionnaire was modified and pilot-tested to include essential information relevant to the study. The researchers obtained permission from the original authors to use and adapt their questionnaires to gather the necessary data on self-efficacy and satisfaction with disaster response simulation-based learning.

Graduate Nursing Students from Batch 2022-2023 were invited to participate in this research endeavor. They were asked to engage in self-reflection to evaluate their self-efficacy and satisfaction with the disaster response simulation-based learning and lectures in order to complete the questionnaire. Systematic random sampling was employed to determine the participants for the study.

The questionnaire was composed of three parts. The first part pertains to the name of the respondent, which is optional, and a statement if they had attended the 5-day lecture on actual disaster response simulation day. The second part of the questionnaire was the checklist of the level of self-efficacy of disaster response simulation-based learnings, which comprises the items of knowledge, skills, and attitude preparedness. The third part of the questionnaire includes a checklist of the level of satisfaction with the disaster response simulation-based learning comprising items about the context, background, and simulation design.

RESULTS

Table 1. The Level of Self-Efficacy of the Participants to the Earthquake Disaster Simulation-Based Learning in terms of Knowledge Preparedness

KNOWLEDGE	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Exposed to an earthquake simulation-based disaster response, I am prepared to		
1. find many solutions to provide care to disaster victim.	2.08	Knowledgeably Prepared
2. manage complicated problems in caring for disaster victim that requires immediate attention.	2.01	Knowledgeably Prepared
3. think of solutions when I find myself in trouble caring for disaster victim.	2.07	Knowledgeably Prepared
4. unite disaster nursing theory with practice.	2.07	Knowledgeably Prepared

5. utilize gained knowledge on communication during disaster response.	2.46	Very Knowledgeably Prepared
6. utilize gained knowledge to promote teamwork during disaster response.	2.54	Very Knowledgeably Prepared
7. utilize gained knowledge on disaster response triaging.	2.38	Very Knowledgeably Prepared
8. utilize gained knowledge on how to stabilize an injured disaster victim.	2.36	Very Knowledgeably Prepared
Overall Mean	2.25	Knowledgeably Prepared

Point Scale	Ranges	Ranges Interpretation
3	2.34 - 3.00	Very Knowledgeably Prepared
2	1.67 - 2.33	Knowledgeably Prepared
1	1.00 - 1.66	Not Knowledgeably Prepared

Table 1 shows that the participants were knowledgeable and prepared to render nursing care to a disaster victim with or without complication. On the utilization of knowledge relating to communication, disaster triaging, and the importance of teamwork during a disaster response, participants were very knowledgeable and prepared. In integrating disaster nursing theory into practice, the participants were knowledgeable and prepared. Overall the participants believe that they are knowledgeable prepared to render care to a disaster victim during a disaster response. Participants were only knowledgeable prepared because they only experienced one earthquake disaster response simulation-based learning.

Comparing the means across the three contexts—attitude, skills, and knowledge—it is evident that knowledge preparedness received the second-highest mean score of 2.25. This indicates that participants perceived themselves as relatively well-prepared in knowledge, trailing slightly behind skills, with the highest mean score. The relatively high mean scores across various knowledge-related items suggest that participants had gained valuable insights and understanding through simulation exercises. They feel equipped to apply theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios, communicate effectively, collaborate in team settings, and perform triaging and injury stabilization tasks.

The participant's ability to unite disaster nursing theory with practice and think of solutions when encountering challenges during simulations underscores the effectiveness of simulation-based learning in bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. It highlighted the importance of experiential learning in enhancing self-efficacy in disaster response contexts.

Simulation-based learning is effective in improving nursing students' perceived competence, self-efficacy, and learning satisfaction. While the primary changes occur at the first simulation effort, it is the accumulated multiple exposure experiences that collectively improve students' learning outcomes. The balance between the frequency of

SBL exposure and students' improvements is an important issue to consider. The findings of this study indicate that students are capable of accumulating nursing competence, self-efficacy, and learning satisfaction over time (Hung et al., 2021).

Table 2. The Level of Self-Efficacy of the Participants to the Earthquake Disaster Simulation-Based Learning in terms of Skills Preparedness

SKILLS	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Exposed to an earthquake simulation-based disaster response, I am prepared to		
1. invest necessary effort to solve most of the disaster victim's problem.	2.23	Skillfully Prepared
2. learn and handle unforeseen situation in a patient care environment.	2.13	Skillfully Prepared
3. achieve or accomplish my goals in caring for disaster victim.	2.22	Skillfully Prepared
4. stabilize disaster victims using bandage and splint application.	2.27	Skillfully Prepared
5. use improvised stretcher or available spinal board for disaster victim transport	2.31	Skillfully Prepared
6. effectively relay information to the team.	2.47	Very Skillfully Prepared
7. effectively communicate with the team.	2.50	Very Skillfully Prepared
8. effectively collaborate and work with peers.	2.41	Very Skillfully Prepared
9. effectively discuss a disaster plan to the team.	2.30	Skillfully Prepared
10. identify and prioritize disaster victims using the triage system.	2.41	Very Skillfully Prepared
11. utilize available resources from my surroundings to make improvised splints, bandages.	2.41	Very Skillfully Prepared
Overall Mean	2.33	Skillfully Prepared

Point Scale	Ranges	Ranges Interpretation
3	2.34 - 3.00	Very Skillfully Prepared
2	1.67 - 2.33	Skillfully Prepared
1	1.00 - 1.66	Not Skillfully Prepared

On skills self-efficacy of the participants, table 2 shows that the participants were very skillfully prepared in terms of making improvised splint and bandages using surrounding available resources. The same is true on the participants' skills in identifying and prioritizing disaster victims using the disaster triage. However, the participants also expressed that they were just skillfully prepared in using bandage and splint application to stabilize the disaster victim, and the use of improvised stretcher or available spinal board for disaster victim transport.

On communication skills of relaying information and to effectively communicate with the team members, the participants were very skillfully prepared.

However, it is worth to note that the participants were just skillfully prepared in utilizing their skills in solving disaster victim problem, handling unforeseen situation during a disaster response, and accomplishing plan goal in taking care of the disaster victims. Participants were only skillfully prepared in utilizing their skills because they were not able to practice it nor were they able to perform a role-play after the lecture prior to the main disaster response simulation-based learning.

Comparing the means across the three contexts—attitude, skills, and knowledge—it is evident that skills preparedness received the highest mean score of 2.33. This indicates that participants perceived themselves as particularly well-prepared regarding skills, surpassing both attitude and knowledge in terms of self-efficacy.

The relatively high mean scores across various skill-related items suggest that participants have gained practical competencies and abilities through simulation exercises. Even though the simulation only took a day, the participants gained the necessary skills and perceived themselves as efficient enough regarding the skills that they learned.

The participants' positive perception of their skills preparedness reflects the immersive and impactful nature of their experiences in disaster simulation-based learning, highlighting the effectiveness of experiential learning in enhancing self-efficacy in disaster response contexts.

It was shown that using simulation after role-play was a more effective teaching method than simulation after lecture across all subdomains except self-efficacy and prudence. Furthermore, engaging nursing students in diverse roles within authentic role-play scenarios alongside simulation activities resulted in a more profound comprehension of clinical contexts and enhanced their self-assurance and analytical abilities. (Kim, 2018)

Table 3. The Level of Self-Efficacy of the Participants to the Earthquake Disaster Simulation-Based Learning in terms of Attitude Preparedness

ATTITUDES	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Exposed to an earthquake simulation-based disaster response, I am prepared to		
1. remain calm when facing difficult disaster victim's care.	2.31	Attitude is Prepared
2. feel confident with the disaster response fidelity resources.	2.32	Attitude is Prepared
3. feel nervous or stressed about my ability to perform well in future disaster response.	2.14	Attitude is Prepared
4. function as a disaster nurse practitioner.	2.16	Attitude is Prepared
5. be confident that I could treat efficiently during unexpected events and emergencies or disaster situations.	2.25	Attitude is Prepared
6. handle whatever difficult disaster situation that will come my way.	2.16	Attitude is Prepared

7. be confident in handling unforeseen situations in a patient care environment	2.16	Attitude is Prepared
8. discover the methods and ways to address the situation tactfully, if a co-worker of family member disagrees with me	2.25	Attitude is Prepared
9. analyze my own behavior and actions during the simulation	2.34	Attitude is Very Prepared
10. be confident that I can decide what correct technique will be used to stabilize disaster victim.	2.23	Attitude is Prepared
Overall Mean	2.24	Attitude is Prepared

Point Scale	Ranges	Ranges Interpretation
3	2.34 - 3.00	Attitude is Very Prepared
2	1.67 - 2.33	Attitude is Prepared
1	1.00 - 1.66	Attitude is Not Prepared

Table 3 is about the participants' self-efficacy in terms of their feelings or attitude about a disaster response. On their confidence to do an earthquake disaster response, the participants' attitude is prepared due to their fidelity simulation-based learning, and the participants are prepared to render efficient care during an unexpected, emergency or disaster situation.

The participants also expressed feelings/attitude of preparedness to function as disaster nurse practitioner and handle difficult disaster situation. Notably, participants feel particularly ready to analyze their own behavior and actions during simulations, suggesting a high level of self-awareness and reflective capacity. On the same note, the participants also express the same attitude that they are prepared to experience stresses or nervousness and to remain calm when faced with difficult disaster victims' problem. Participants attitude were only prepared because they were not able to practice their skills nor were they able to perform their role after the lecture prior to the main disaster response simulation-based learning drill.

Comparing the means across the three contexts—attitude, skills, and knowledge—it is evident that attitude preparedness received the lowest mean score of 2.24. This indicates that participants perceive themselves as less prepared in terms of attitudes compared to skills and knowledge in the context of disaster response.

The participants' experience in an earthquake disaster simulation-based learning and their perception of attitude preparedness are significant. While participants may have gained practical skills and knowledge through simulation exercises, their attitudes toward handling difficult situations may still be evolving. It is plausible that attitudes are formed over time through repeated exposure to various scenarios and reflective debriefing sessions.

While attitude preparedness may have received the lowest mean score among the three contexts, it is important to recognize that attitudes are malleable and can be positively influenced through continued exposure, reflection, and learning in disaster simulation-based learning environments.

It is believed that the attitude toward disaster management changed positively because the research participants recognized the need for training to prepare for disasters by identifying potential risks that could lead to disasters and establishing disaster plans. Therefore, there is a need to positively change the attitude of nursing students toward disaster management by conducting various simulation-based disaster situation management education in the undergraduate curriculum. (Lee et al.,2022)

Table 4. Overall Self-Efficacy of the Participants to the Earthquake Disaster Simulation-Based Learning in terms Knowledge, Skills, Attitude Preparedness

Self-Efficacy	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Knowledge Preparedness	2.25	Knowledgeably Prepared
Preparedness Skills	2.33	Skillfully Prepared
Attitude Preparedness	2.24	Attitude is Prepared
Overall Mean	2.27	Prepared

Table 4 shows that participants in the earthquake disaster simulation-based learning perceive themselves as generally prepared, with an overall self-efficacy mean of 2.27. Among the three dimensions assessed, preparedness skills received the highest rating (2.33), indicating that participants feel relatively confident in their ability to apply practical disaster response skills. Knowledge preparedness followed closely with a mean of 2.25, suggesting that while participants have a foundational understanding of disaster response protocols, further reinforcement may be needed. Attitude preparedness received the lowest mean score (2.24), implying that while participants believe they have the right mindset, they may require additional training to enhance their confidence and mental readiness in high-pressure emergency situations. These results highlight the need for further improvements in disaster simulation-based learning to strengthen participants' self-efficacy in all three aspects knowledge, skills, and attitude to ensure a more effective and well-rounded disaster response capability.

Table 5. The Level of Self-Satisfaction of the Participants to the Earthquake Disaster Simulation-Based Learning in terms of Context

CONTEXT	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. I am able to ask questions to improve my knowledge and understanding.	2.34	Very Satisfied
2. I am able to have quality feedback of the process and my performance.	2.40	Very Satisfied

Overall Mean	2.37	Very Satisfied
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Point Scale	Ranges	Ranges Interpretation
3	2.34 - 3.00	Very Satisfied
2	1.67 - 2.33	Satisfied
1	1.00 - 1.66	Unsatisfied

Table 5 shows that participants in the earthquake disaster simulation-based learning reported a high level of self-satisfaction, with an overall mean of 2.37, interpreted as "Very Satisfied." The highest-rated aspect was the quality of feedback on the process and performance, with a mean score of 2.40, indicating that participants highly valued the feedback they received during the simulation. The ability to ask questions to enhance knowledge and understanding followed closely with a mean of 2.34, also interpreted as "Very Satisfied," suggesting that participants felt encouraged to engage in discussions and clarify uncertainties. These results indicate that the simulation-based learning approach was effective in fostering an interactive and supportive learning environment, reinforcing participants' confidence and comprehension in disaster response preparedness.

Table 6. The Level of Self-Satisfaction of the Participants to the Earthquake Disaster Simulation-Based Learning in terms of Background

BACKGROUND	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. The simulation design was appropriate for student's specific level of knowledge and skills.	2.41	Very Satisfied
2. The disaster triaging scenario resembled a real-life situation.	2.41	Very Satisfied
3. I am able to perform the needed actions within the specific time of simulation.	2.44	Very Satisfied
Overall Mean	2.42	Very Satisfied

Point Scale	Ranges	Ranges Interpretation
3	2.34 - 3.00	Very Satisfied
2	1.67 - 2.33	Satisfied
1	1.00 - 1.66	Unsatisfied

Table 6 shows that the participants' self-satisfaction in an earthquake disaster simulation-based learning reveals that the background received the same highest mean as the simulation design and context. It shows that the participants are very satisfied in achieving their simulation-based learning expectations, that the simulation-based learning is designed according to participants' level of knowledge and skills, that the simulation-based learning resources and application of disaster triaging is as close to a real-life scenario, and that simulation-based learning disaster response was

accomplished within the predetermined time frame. This suggests that the simulation-based learning scenarios was relevant and challenging, mirroring real-life situations.

Table 7. The Level of Self-Satisfaction of the Participants to the Earthquake Disaster Simulation-Based Learning in terms of Simulation Design

SIMULATION DESIGN	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. The provided learning materials and simulation activities promoted a future learning.	2.50	Very Satisfied
2. The bandages and improvised stretchers or the available spinal boards were efficient in stabilizing the disaster victim.	2.40	Very Satisfied
3. The carrying technique designed to transport disaster victim was sufficiently working.	2.42	Very Satisfied
4. The disaster communication technique was efficiently working.	2.36	Very Satisfied
5. The materials used to make an improvised stretcher for disaster victim transport was efficiently working.	2.41	Very Satisfied
6. The use of an available spinal board for victim transport was efficiently working.	2.38	Very Satisfied
Overall Mean	2.42	Very Satisfied

Point Scale	Ranges	Ranges Interpretation
3	2.34 - 3.00	Very Satisfied
2	1.67 - 2.33	Satisfied
1	1.00 - 1.66	Unsatisfied

Table 7 shows that participants in the earthquake disaster simulation-based learning reported a high level of self-satisfaction in terms of simulation design, with an overall mean of 2.42, interpreted as "Very Satisfied." The highest-rated aspect was the effectiveness of learning materials and activities in promoting future learning (WM = 2.50), highlighting their relevance in disaster preparedness. Other key elements, such as the efficiency of bandages and spinal boards in stabilizing victims (WM = 2.40) and the carrying techniques for victim transport (WM = 2.42), also received high satisfaction ratings. These results suggest that the simulation design effectively provided hands-on experience, reinforcing participants' confidence and skills in disaster response.

Table 8. Overall Self-Satisfaction of the Participants to the Earthquake Disaster Simulation-Based Learning in terms of Context, Background, and Simulation Design

Self-Satisfaction	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Context	2.37	Very Satisfied
2. Background	2.42	Very Satisfied
3. Simulation Design	2.42	Very Satisfied
Overall Mean	2.40	Very Satisfied

Table 8 shows that participants in the earthquake disaster simulation-based learning reported a high level of self-satisfaction across context, background, and simulation design, with an overall mean of 2.40, interpreted as "Very Satisfied." Among the three aspects, background and simulation design received the highest ratings (WM = 2.42), indicating that participants found the provided information and structure of the simulation highly effective. The context also received a "Very Satisfied" rating (WM = 2.37), suggesting that the scenarios used were relevant and realistic. These results highlight the overall effectiveness of the simulation in providing a well-structured and engaging learning experience for disaster preparedness.

Table 9. Significant Relationship Between the Self-Efficacy and Self-Satisfaction of the Participants to the Earthquake Disaster Response Simulation-based Learning

Variables	Spearman rho	Strength of Correlation	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
The self-efficacy and self-satisfaction of the participants to the disaster response simulation-based learning	0.704935	Fairly Strong Positive	.00001	The result is a significant correlation	Do reject null hypothesis

Table 9 shows the significant relationship between self-efficacy and self-satisfaction of participants in the earthquake disaster response simulation-based learning. The Spearman rho value of 0.704935 indicates a fairly strong positive correlation, suggesting that higher self-efficacy is associated with higher self-satisfaction. With a p-value of .00001, the result is statistically significant, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This finding implies that participants who felt more confident in their disaster response abilities also reported greater satisfaction with the simulation experience.

Findings

The findings of this study directly address the research questions outlined in the statement of the problem:

1. Self-Efficacy Levels in an Earthquake Disaster Response Simulation-Based Learning:

Participants demonstrated a commendable level of self-efficacy across various domains crucial for disaster response, including knowledge, skills, and attitudes preparedness towards emergencies.

It is noticeable, however, that the participants are just knowledgeably prepared to find solutions to provide care management to a disaster victim with or without complicated conditions. The participants' self-efficacy in an earthquake disaster simulation-based learning reveals an interesting perspective on their preparedness across knowledge, skills, and attitude domains. Participants rated their skills preparedness the highest, indicating confidence in applying practical skills learned during simulations. Nonetheless, participants are just skillfully prepared to stabilize disaster victims using bandages and splint applications, and the same in transporting disaster victims using an improvised stretcher. Conversely, knowledge preparedness ranked slightly lower, suggesting room for improvement in translating theoretical knowledge into practical application. Attitude preparedness received the lowest mean, suggesting ongoing confidence, resilience, and adaptability development when faced with challenging scenarios—also, attitude formed over time. The relationship between participants' experience in simulation-based learning and their perception of preparedness underscores the importance of continued exposure, reflective debriefing, and tailored interventions to enhance overall self-efficacy. While participants feel relatively well-prepared regarding skills and knowledge, continued support is crucial to developing attitudes for effective disaster response.

2. Satisfaction Levels in an Earthquake Disaster Response Simulation-Based Learning:

Overall, participants represented high levels of satisfaction with the earthquake disaster response simulation-based learning experience, particularly regarding the learning context, background information provided, and simulation design.

The participants found the background and simulation design well-structured and effective, as evidenced by their equally high ratings. This indicates that participants appreciated the relevance and realism of the scenarios presented and the efficiency of the simulation tools and techniques. While still rated as "Very Satisfied," the context received a slightly lower score, suggesting that participants may have perceived some areas for improvement regarding the learning

environment, feedback mechanisms, or the facilitation of discussions and interactions.

Despite the high levels of satisfaction overall, the fact that none of the scores reached the maximum suggests that there are areas within all three components that could be refined or enhanced. These areas will not get the maximum score if self-efficacy does not reach the very prepared level, as the data results prove that these two variables are related.

In connection to the participants' experience in disaster simulation-based learning, these findings highlight the significance of a well-rounded instructional approach. A positive learning experience, characterized by effective context, relevant background, and efficient simulation design, is crucial for engaging participants, facilitating skill development, and ensuring the training program's success. The slight variation in satisfaction levels among the different components provides valuable insights for further refining and optimizing the learning experience better to meet the needs and expectations of the participants

Conclusions

The findings indicate that participants have a commendable level of self-efficacy. Participation in an earthquake disaster response simulation-based learning (SBL) significantly enhances their self-efficacy across various domains of preparedness, including knowledge, skills, and attitudes. However, since the overall self-efficacy of the participants is only moderately prepared, improvements are necessary to better prepare them for SBL and actual disaster responses.

Additionally, the high levels of satisfaction reported by participants highlight the importance of simulation-based learning in providing an engaging and impactful educational experience.

The significant positive correlation between self-efficacy and satisfaction further underscores the interdependence of these factors in shaping students' perceptions of their preparedness. These findings have important implications for nursing education, suggesting that incorporating SBL into the curriculum can enhance students' confidence and competence in disaster response. Moreover, it is crucial for educators to continue integrating SBL into nursing programs and to further explore the relationship between self-efficacy, satisfaction, and preparedness. This approach aims to optimize educational outcomes and ultimately improve patient care during emergencies.

Recommendations

In conclusion, based on the findings of this study, the researchers recommend the following:

1. Diversify the frequency and types of simulation-based learning scenarios.

Introducing a wider variety of disaster scenarios, beyond just earthquakes, can enhance participants' ability to respond to different types of emergencies. Scenarios could include mass road accidents, fire incidents, pandemic outbreaks, mass poisoning events, and bombings. By conducting more frequent small group simulations prior to larger disaster response drills, we can provide students with a more comprehensive training experience. This approach will improve their knowledge, skills, and attitude toward disaster response, equipping them to manage various challenges posed by different emergencies, including natural disasters, mass casualties, pandemics, and terrorist incidents.

2. Ensure Participation in Simulation-Based Learning:

To enhance learning and skill development, it's important to ensure the active involvement of all participants. This can be achieved by adjusting group dynamics, rotating participants through different roles, and incorporating various scenarios to meet the diverse educational needs of individuals. Additionally, introducing real-time challenges or complications during the simulation keeps participants engaged and fosters quick thinking and adaptability.

3. Enhance the Debriefing and Feedback Process:

Enhancing post-simulation debriefing sessions can encourage deeper student reflection and learning. Providing structured feedback from instructors and peers offers valuable insights that help students identify areas for growth and reinforce their learning. For instance, utilizing a structured debriefing framework such as the Advocacy-Inquiry method or the Plus-Delta model, along with video playback, enables participants to observe their actions and decisions in real time, allowing them to pinpoint areas for improvement.

4. Utilize Advanced Technological Tools:

Integrating innovative tools such as virtual reality simulations, augmented reality simulations, mobile applications for simulation training, and simulation-based gaming platforms can significantly enhance the realism and effectiveness of disaster response simulation-based learning (SBL) for future cohorts of student nurses. These advancements offer engaging educational experiences, allowing learners to refine their skills in a carefully controlled environment.

5. Expose participants to real offices or agencies involved in emergency response by establishing shadowing programs where they are paired with emergency response professionals for a period of time. This allows participants to observe individuals in various roles, such as incident commanders, emergency medical technicians, or dispatchers, gaining valuable insights into their responsibilities and decision-making processes.

By implementing these recommendations, educational institutions can enhance the quality of disaster response simulation-based learning for graduate nursing students, better preparing them to handle emergencies confidently and competently in their future professional careers.

Compliance with Ethical Consideration

The researchers had undergone an ethics review at the Holy Name University Ethics Review Committee prior to the commencement of the research. In conducting the study, the researchers had secured permission from the researchers' adviser and the Dean of the College of Health Sciences. The researchers were also granted permission by the participants to proceed, ask, and gather data. After collecting the data, the researchers ensured the participants that the gathered data were strictly confidential.

Confidentiality and anonymity were preserved throughout the research process. This study ensured anonymity by not disclosing the participants' names in the questionnaire and research report. Confidentiality, likewise, was maintained by keeping the collected data in a sealed envelope and not revealing the participants' identities when reporting or publishing the study. No information was identified in the questionnaires, and the questionnaires were numbered only after the data was collected

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